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Research Article

**DIFFUSION-WEIGHTED MEGNETIC RESONANCE
IMAGING IN FOCAL HEPATIC LESIONS**¹Dr. Hassan Bukhari, ²Dr. Syed Anjum Mehdi, ³Dr. Mohammad Haris Tipu¹ Senior Registrar Radiology, Allied Hospital, Faisalabad.²Associate Professor Radiology, Allied Hospital, Punjab Medical College, Faisalabad.³Medical Officer, Govt. General Hospital Samman abad, Faisalabad.**Abstract:***Objective: To determine diagnostic accuracy of diffusion-weighted (DW) MRI in focal lesions of liver.**Study design: Cross-sectional study.**Setting & Duration: Study was conducted in Department of Radiology, Allied Hospital, Punjab Medical College, Faisalabad for the period from 1st January, 2014 to 30th June, 2016.**Sample size: 382 cases.**Material & Methods: All patients were examined with ultrasound and immediately thereafter with 1.5 Tesla whole body MR imager, (DWI and ADC images were taken).**Results: Mean age of the patients was 57.3±9.7 year. Distribution of patients by gender showed 65.4% (n= 250) male and 34.5 % (n=132) female patients. Of the total 382 patients, hepatic lesions were detected in 300 patients and of those three hundred hepatic lesions, 175 were hepato cellular carcinoma, 50 metastatic lesions, 11 adenomas, 12 FNH, 16 hemangiomata and 36 were hepatic cysts. Sensitivity, Specificity and Diagnostic accuracy of (DW) MRI is 94.34%, 85.71% and 94% respectively.**Conclusion: Diffusion-weighted imaging is a valuable tool, for both expert & novice radiologists, in early diagnosis of hepatic focal lesion.**Key words: Hepatic focal lesion, Diffusion-weighted MRI, ADC***Corresponding author:****Dr. Hassan Bukhari,**
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INTRODUCTION:

Hepatic focal lesion can be seen as both benign and malignant. A liver lesion detected in a patient with a known malignant disease requires a further assessment, as the liver is common site for metastatic spread and these lesions are encountered in about 25% of the population [1]. The detection, characterization and accurate differentiation of these lesions have always been one of the goals of different imaging methods [2]. Now a day's variety of diagnostic imaging technique is currently available for diagnosis of focal liver lesions like ultrasonography (USG) and computed tomography (CT). Additionally, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is preferred if further characterization of these masses is needed. MRI has many advantages (e.g., high contrast resolution, the ability to obtain images in any plane, lack of ionizing radiation, and the safety of using particulate contrast media rather than those containing iodine) that make it a favored modality [2,3]. MRI provides excellent tissue contrast, which is much greater than that of any other imaging modality. Focal nodular lesions characterization with MRI is based on their morphology, signal intensity on different sequences and in their behavior with paramagnetic contrast agents [4].

Diffusion-weighted MRI, that not requires contrast agents, is widely applied in central nervous system lesions. However, it is now available for abdominal evaluations as well; including diffuse and focal diseases of the liver [5]. Diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) relies on measuring diffusion of water molecules in the tissue by MRI. It is sensitive to very small scale motion of water molecules at microscopic level. Diffusion is quantitatively reflected in a diffusion coefficient. Diffusion coefficients in DWI are reflected in the apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) expressed in mm^2/s . [3] Measurements of ADC values is useful in the characterization of focal liver lesions. In the literature, ADC values vary between $0.94\text{-}2.85 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ for metastases and $0.69\text{-}2.28 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ for normal liver parenchyma [6]. The sensitivity, specificity and accuracy of Diffusion-weighted MR imaging for focal liver lesions is 96.7%, 87.8% and 90.7% respectively [7]. DWI alone performs equally well as Gd-MRI in detection and differentiation of different hepatic focal lesions. In cases where gadolinium injection is contraindicated, dynamic contrast-enhanced imaging can be replaced by unenhanced T1 and T2 weighted imaging

combined with DWI. Adding DWI to Gd-MRI is more accurate, indicating that it should be included in oncologic liver MRI [8].

As Diffusion-weighted MRI neither requires contrast agents nor any invasive diagnostic procedure. The purpose of this study was to describe the diagnostic accuracy of DWI MRI that will not only limit the number of pure diagnostic biopsies in focal liver lesions but will also help in the selection of proper treatment option.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

382 patients referred from indoor and OPDs to the Radiology Department of Allied Hospital Faisalabad, were included in this study, fulfilling the criteria.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

All patients with focal liver lesions of any size on ultrasound or Computed Tomography Scan. Patients of age more than 25 years of either sex (Age limit of 25-80).

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

Patients on chemotherapy for primary or secondary hepatic neoplasm.
Patients having multiple focal lesions and large amount of ascities or pleural effusion due to their distinct motion artifacts.
Patients who are unable to maintain a breath-hold or have contraindication to MRI i.e. MRI incompatible prosthesis or cardiac pacemaker holders.

After taking informed consent and relevant history, diffusion-weighted MRI performed in every patient by using 1.5 Tesla MR System. DW-MR images obtained in all patients using 2D breath-hold T2-weighted half-Fourier acquisition single shot turbo spin-echo (HASTE), breath-hold T2-weighted turbo spin-echo (TSE) and dynamic contrast-enhanced 3D gradient-echo (volumetric interpolated breath-hold examination, VIBE) sequences. All the sequences done during a single breath-hold, at two b values ($0 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, $1000 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$). DW-MRI findings confirmed by histopathology report to pathology department of Allied hospital Faisalabad and confirmed by consultant pathologist.

All the data entered and analyzed by using SPSS Version -10. Mean and standard deviation calculated for quantitative variables i.e. age, ADC values. Frequency and percentage

calculated for qualitative variables i.e. gender and true positive. 2×2 contingency table used to calculate the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value and diagnostic accuracy.

RESULTS

Of the total of 382 patients, majority were between 41-70 years of age and least number of patients were 30-40 years old with mean age of 57.3±9.7 year (Table-1).

Table-1: Distribution of patients by age(n=382)

Age (Year)	Number of Cases	Percentage
30-40	30	7.8 %
41-50	60	15.7 %
51-60	200	52.3 %
61-70	92	24 %
Total	382	100.0
Mean±SD	57.3±9.7	

Distribution of patients by gender showed 250 (65.4%) male and 132(34.5%) females. (Table-2). The mean age of the patients was 57.3±9.7 year and out of 382 patients, hepatic lesions were detected in 300 patients. Out of these 300 hepatic lesions, 175 were having HCC, 50 Metastatic lesions, 11 adenomas, 12 FNH, 15 hemangiomata and 36 were hepatic cysts. Sensitivity, Specificity and Diagnostic Accuracy of DW MRI are 94.34%, 85.71% and 94% respectively. Mean size of largest lesion was 1.75±0.9 cm in present study.

Table-2: Distribution of patients by gender (n=382)

Gender	Number of Cases	Percentage
Male	250	65.5 %
Female	132	34.5 %
Total	382	100.0

Table-3: Types of focal hepatic lesions (n=300)

Site	Number of Cases	Percentage
HCC	175	58.3 %
Metastasis	53	17.6 %
Adenoma	11	3.6 %
Focal nodular hyperplasia	12	4 %
Hemangioma	15	5 %
Hepatic cysts	36	12 %
Total	300	100

Hepatic Focal lesion on DW MRI versus HISTOPATHOLOGY (n=300)

Sensitivity= $TP/TP+FP \times 100=94.34\%$

Specificity = $TN/FN+TN \times 100=85.71\%$

PPV= $TP/TP+FP \times 100=98\%$

NPP= $TN/FN+TN \times 100= 66.67\%$

DA= $TP+TN/TP+FP+TN+FN \times 100=93.33\%$

Examples of different types of lesions & them diffusion weighted images seen in Figures-1 & 2:

Figure-1:

A: T1-weighted MRI; B: T2-weighted MRI; C: Diffusion weighted image (b-value 50 s/mm²); D: Diffusion weighted image (b-value 1000 s/mm²) in a 33-year old woman with a haemangiomas lesion.

Figure-2:

MRI and DWI of an adenoma and a hemangioma. A: T1-weighted MRI; B: T2-weighted MRI; C: Diffusion weighted image (b-value 50 s/mm²); D: Diffusion weighted image (b-value 1000 s/mm²) in a 41-year-old women with multiple liver lesions.

DICUSSION:

The studies including Latif et al [9] have suggested that the measurement of ADC values is useful in the characterization of focal liver lesions. Reduced ADC values have been reported for most malignant tumors and increased values in benign hepatic lesions [9]. This finding is thought to be the result of cellular membranes impeding the mobility of water molecules. However, solid benign lesions, which are also highly cellular, exhibit decreased ADC values as well. Abscesses do so too because their viscose content with bacteria, inflammatory cells, mucoid proteins and cell debris result in restricted diffusion, thus low ADC values. On the other hand, necrotic and

cystic malignancies show high ADC values resulting from larger diffusion distances as a consequence of lost membrane integrity. Benign lesions as simple cysts & hemangioma show high ADC values because of liquid content & large extracellular spaces. Although a significant difference was revealed between benign and solid malignant lesion, the ADC values were dispersed and difficult to point the practical threshold ADC value. Finally, the dMRI and the ADC measurements should not be considered as unique assessment criteria of the FHLs. Other MRI protocols and histological findings should be useful in this regards. Larger multi-centric studies with standardized protocol might help in improving the determinacy of the dMRI in the FHLs. According to Feuerlein et al

[10], the pretest probability of malignancy is very important in the determination to which degree a large ADC value is predictive for a malignancy, i.e. the history, demography and clinical picture of the individual patient. Even ADC values of lesions of the same kind show overlap and there is no cut-off value for ADC values in normal parenchyma, benign and malignant lesions. In the literature, ADC values vary between $0.94\text{-}2.85 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ for metastases and $0.69\text{-}2.28 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ for normal liver parenchyma. This is mainly because every study group uses their own scanning parameters. Differences in b-values are the main cause of non-equivocal results. Breath-hold, respiratory triggered and navigator echo techniques can also give different ADC values. There is need for a uniformly applicable scanning protocol to eliminate discrepancies in ADC values caused by different scanning parameters. Parikh *et al* [11] reported a significantly higher overall lesion detection rate for breath-hold or respiratory triggered DWI than for conventional T2-weighted MRI (88% vs 70%). Bruegel *et al* [12] compared respiratory DWI-EPI with T2-TSE. They found a sensitivity and specificity for T2-TSE MRI of 45%-62% for unenhanced MRI and 88%-91% for DWI-EPI for lesions > 10 mm. When considering only small metastases < 10 mm, the differences between DWI and conventional MRI with and without contrast are even more pronounced: a sensitivity of 85% for DWI-EPI and 26%-44% for T2-TSE. The impact of the dMRI seems to be promising in the diagnostic strategy; however, is still in the evaluation stage. Nevertheless, it should be included in the routine hepatic imaging protocols. The use of the dMRI, and particularly the ADC measurement in the characterization of the focal hepatic lesions with the differentiating benign and malignant lesions is confirmed in a study conducted by Oussous *et al* [13]. In our study, sensitivity, specificity and Diagnostic Accuracy is 94.34%, 85.71% and 94% respectively. The results of our study are comparable with DM yang *et al* [7]. Diffusion-weighted imaging in the liver is a relative new and increasingly used imaging technique in addition to conventional unenhanced and contrast enhanced MRI. Diffusion-weighted imaging is useful in the detection of small HCC in the cirrhotic liver, with higher sensitivity, specificity and positive predictive value compared to conventional contrast enhanced imaging due to better lesion to liver contrast and background suppression of signals arising from

vessels and bile ducts

CONCLUSION:

Diffusion-weighted imaging is a valuable tool, for both expert and novice radiologists, in the early diagnosis of hepatic focal lesion

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